

Energy Efficiency of a Resistor-Fractional Order Capacitor Series Circuit During Charging from a DC Voltage Source

Berk Mercan^{1,ö}

^{1-3*}Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Faculty of Çorlu Engineering, Tekirdağ Namık Kemal University, Tekirdağ, Türkiye.

To cite this article:

Berk Mercan, Alperen Hoçur and Reşat Mutlu. “Energy Efficiency of a Resistor-Fractional Order Capacitor Series Circuit During Charging from a DC Voltage Source”, *Parana Journal of Science and Education*. Vol. 12, No. 2, 2026, pp. 1-9.

Received: January 27, 2026; **Accepted:** March 21, 2026; **Published:** April 3, 2026.

Abstract

Fractional-order derivatives offer a significant advantage in modeling complex electrical and electronic systems by providing higher accuracy and flexibility compared to classical integer-order derivative approaches. This method allows for the precise description of the dynamic behavior of energy storing circuit elements, particularly supercapacitors. In recent years, the fractional-order circuit elements have found widespread use in a wide range of applications, from filter designs and control systems to energy storage applications and signal processing. In this study, the energy loss incurred during the charging of a capacitor, modeled using a fractional-order derivative element in series with a resistor and driven by a DC source, is analytically examined. The analysis is conducted using the Caputo definition of the fractional derivative. The results are then compared with the energy loss in a classical R–C circuit. The findings indicate that the energy loss in a fractional-order capacitor-resistor circuit during charging differs from that in an integer-order counterpart. It is found to be dependent on the fractional order α . Fractional-order modeling of the capacitor is needed to calculate the charging efficiency of such a circuit accurately.

Keywords: Charging Dynamics, R-C Circuit Analysis, Energy Efficiency, Fractional-Order Derivative, Fractional-Order Capacitor, Caputo Derivative.

¹ Email: 1230657013@nku.edu.tr

[¥] Email: 1240657801@nku.edu.tr

[£] Email: rmutlu@nku.edu.tr (Corresponding Author)

1. Introduction

Fractional-order derivatives are extensively applied in the modeling and control of engineering systems [1-3]. They are useful in modeling biological systems [2, 4]. Capacitors can be modeled using the fractional derivatives [5]. Some fractional order circuit elements can be made using emulators [6, 7]. Supercapacitors can be modeled using fractional order models [8-12]. It is more difficult to examine circuits with fractional order capacitors than those circuits with LTI capacitors [13-18]. They require methods for examination not taught in the undergraduate circuit theory courses [19-21]. Analytical solutions of various electrical circuits with fractional derivatives can be found in [15-18, 20]. Caputo fractional-order derivative is commonly used in the analysis of electrical circuits with fractional order capacitors [21].

1.1 Capacitors

Capacitors are fundamentally designed to store energy, making energy-related analysis a critical aspect across all capacitor types, including linear time-invariant (LTI) capacitors, supercapacitors, and fractional-order capacitors [22-24]. The expression for stored energy in an LTI capacitor is well established in standard textbooks. Numerous studies in the literature have investigated the performance and efficiency of circuits incorporating LTI capacitors [22, 25]. When an uncharged LTI capacitor is connected to a DC voltage source, its voltage increases from zero to the supply level. Reference [25] demonstrates that the total energy required for charging such a capacitor is independent of the resistance in the circuit shown in Figure 1. Regardless of the series resistance, the charging efficiency of an LTI capacitor from a DC source is consistently 50%. This efficiency remains unchanged even if the series resistance varies with time. In essence, half of the supplied energy is stored in the capacitor, while the other half is dissipated as heat [26]. With the emergence of new circuit elements such as fractional-order capacitors, it becomes essential to investigate their energy storage characteristics as well. In [27], the stored energy in a supercapacitor modeled with a fractional order derivative is examined. A study presented in [28] addresses the charging efficiency of a capacitor modeled using the conformable fractional derivative. To the best of our knowledge, the

energy loss of a series fractional capacitor and an LTI resistor ($R-C_\alpha$) has not been examined using the Caputo derivative in the literature yet. The purpose of this study is to obtain the solution of the series resistor-fractional order capacitor circuit supplied by a DC voltage source using the Caputo fractional order derivative, and examine its loss energy and energy efficiency during the charging using the solution. The energy loss is examined for the different orders of the fractional derivative. The differential equation which describes the circuit is given and it is examined whether it has an analytical solution or not. The energy and energy efficiency of the circuit are analyzed for various fractional order α values to understand how a fractional capacitor behaves over time. Its charging efficiency is evaluated in comparison to that of a conventional LTI capacitor. The circuit waveforms are drawn with Python.

The paper is arranged as follows. The fractional-order capacitor model and the differential equation of the series $R-C_\alpha$ circuit given in the second section. The analysis of the fractional-order capacitor-resistor series circuit is presented in the third section. The lost energy is calculated in the fourth section. The simulation results of the circuit are given, and its energy loss is examined for the various fractional orders using the analytical solutions in the fifth section. The paper is finalized with the conclusions section.

2. The Fractional-order Capacitor Model and the Differential Equation of the Series Circuit

The circuit examined in this study is shown in Figure 1. It consists of a fractional order capacitor C_α and a resistor R connected in series and supplied with DC voltage source V_{dc} . For $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, the constitutive law of a fractional capacitor of order α is described by:

$$i_{C_\alpha}(t) = C_\alpha \frac{d^\alpha v_{C_\alpha}(t)}{dt^\alpha} \quad (1)$$

where $i_{C_\alpha}(t)$, $v_{C_\alpha}(t)$, and C_α are the current, the voltage, and the capacitance coefficient of the fractional capacitor, respectively.

For $\alpha=1$, it turns into an LTI capacitor. whose constitutive law is given as

$$i_c(t) = C \frac{dv_c(t)}{dt} \quad (2)$$

For $\alpha = 1$, The $R-C_\alpha$ series circuit shown in Figure 1 turns into the well-know $R-C$ series circuit shown in Figure 2. R is the resistance value in the circuit, and C is the capacitance of the LTI capacitor in the circuit.

Figure 1. The $R-C_\alpha$ series circuit.

Source: Authors.

Figure 2. The $R-C$ series circuit.

Source: Authors.

Using the KCL,

$$i_{C_\alpha}(t) = i_R(t) \quad (3)$$

Using the KVL,

$$V_{dc} = v_{C_\alpha}(t) + v_R(t) \quad (4)$$

where V_{DC} is the voltage of the DC power supply

By combining the terminal equations of the circuit elements and Kirchhoff's Laws, the fractional differential equation describing the circuit is obtained as:

$$V_{dc} = v_{C_\alpha}(t) + R i_{C_\alpha}(t) \quad (5)$$

$$V_{dc} = v_{C_\alpha}(t) + R C_\alpha \frac{d^\alpha v_{C_\alpha}(t)}{dt^\alpha} \quad (6)$$

$$V_{dc} = v_{C_\alpha}(t) + \tau_\alpha \frac{d^\alpha v_{C_\alpha}(t)}{dt^\alpha} \quad (7)$$

(where $\tau_\alpha = R C_\alpha$)

3. The Solution of the Charging Circuit

By taking Laplace transformations of each side of Eq. (7),

$$L\{V_{dc}\} = L\left\{v_{C_\alpha}(t) + \tau_\alpha \frac{d^\alpha v_{C_\alpha}(t)}{dt^\alpha}\right\} \quad (8)$$

Using the following Laplace transformations,

$$L\{v_{C_\alpha}(t)\} = V_{C_\alpha}(s) \quad (9)$$

$$L\left\{\frac{d^\alpha v_{C_\alpha}(t)}{dt^\alpha}\right\} = s^\alpha V_{C_\alpha}(s) - s^{\alpha-1} v_{C_\alpha}(0) \quad (10)$$

$$L\{V_{dc}\} = V_{dc}/s \quad (11)$$

The circuit equation in the Laplace domain is given as follows;

$$\frac{V_{dc}}{s} = V_{C_\alpha}(s) + \tau_\alpha (s^\alpha V_{C_\alpha}(s) - s^{\alpha-1} v_{C_\alpha}(0)) \quad (12)$$

If the initial capacitor voltage is zero,

$$\frac{V_{dc}}{s} = V_{C_\alpha}(s) + \tau_\alpha s^\alpha V_{C_\alpha}(s) = (1 + \tau_\alpha s^\alpha) V_{C_\alpha}(s) \quad (13)$$

$$V_{C_\alpha}(s) = \frac{\frac{V_{dc}}{s}}{1 + \tau_\alpha s^\alpha} = \frac{V_{dc}}{s(1 + \tau_\alpha s^\alpha)} \quad (14)$$

If we return to the time domain using the inverse Laplace transform,

$$V_{C_\alpha}(t) = L^{-1}\{V_{C_\alpha}(s)\} = L^{-1}\left\{\frac{V_{dc}}{s(1 + \tau_\alpha s^\alpha)}\right\} \quad (15)$$

$$V_{C_\alpha}(t) = V_{dc} \left(1 - E_\alpha\left(-\frac{t^\alpha}{RC_\alpha}\right)\right) \quad (16)$$

Where E_α is the Mittag-Leffler function.

The resistor voltage is found as

$$V_R(t) = V_{dc} - V_{C_\alpha}(t) = V_{dc} E_\alpha\left(-\frac{t^\alpha}{RC_\alpha}\right) \quad (17)$$

$$\begin{aligned} I_{C_\alpha} &= L\{i_{C_\alpha}(t)\} = L\left\{C_\alpha \frac{d^\alpha v_{C_\alpha}(t)}{dt^\alpha}\right\} = \\ &= C_\alpha (s^\alpha V_{C_\alpha}(s) - s^{\alpha-1} v_{C_\alpha}(0)) \quad (18) \end{aligned}$$

$$I_{C_\alpha} = C_\alpha (s^\alpha V_{C_\alpha}(s) - s^{\alpha-1} V_{C_\alpha}(0)) \quad (19)$$

Using the zero initial condition,

$$I_{C_\alpha} = C_\alpha s^\alpha V_{C_\alpha}(s) = C_\alpha V_{dc} \frac{s^\alpha}{s(1+\tau_\alpha s^\alpha)} \quad (20)$$

Then, the capacitor current in time domain is found as:

$$\begin{aligned} i_{C_\alpha} &= \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left\{ C_\alpha V_{dc} \frac{s^{\alpha-1}}{(1+\tau_\alpha s^\alpha)} \right\} = \\ &= C_\alpha V_{dc} \mathcal{L}^{-1} \left\{ \frac{s^{\alpha-1}}{(1+\tau_\alpha s^\alpha)} \right\} \quad (21) \end{aligned}$$

$$i_{C_\alpha} = \frac{C_\alpha V_{dc}}{\tau_\alpha} E_\alpha \left(-\frac{t^\alpha}{RC_\alpha} \right) = \frac{V_{dc}}{R} E_\alpha \left(-\frac{t^\alpha}{RC_\alpha} \right) \quad (22)$$

An LTI capacitor supplied by a DC voltage source is shown in Figure 2. The solution of the R-C series circuit supplied by a DC voltage is well-known. The current and voltage of the LTI capacitor are equal to

$$V_c(t) = V_{DC} (1 - e^{-t/(RC)}) \quad (23)$$

and

$$i_c(t) = \frac{V_{DC} e^{-t/(RC)}}{R} \quad (24)$$

For $\alpha = 1$, Eqs. (16) and (22) become Eqs. (23) and (24), respectively.

The two-parameter Mittag-Leffler function, $E_{\alpha,\beta}(z)$, has the following generalized power series expansion;

$$E_{\alpha,\beta}(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{\Gamma(\alpha k + \beta)} \quad (25)$$

For the one-parameter form used in Eq. (16), we have $\beta=1$;

$$E_\alpha(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{\Gamma(\alpha k + 1)} \quad (26)$$

By setting the fractional order to $\alpha = 1$;

$$E_1(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{\Gamma(k+1)} \quad (27)$$

Utilizing the property of the Gamma function that $\Gamma(k+1) = k!$ for positive integers k :

$$E_1(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{k!} \quad (28)$$

This series is the Taylor expansion of the

exponential function, e^z . Thus, the fundamental reduction identity is established:

$$E_1(z) = e^z \quad (29)$$

We apply $\alpha=1$ and set $C_\alpha=C$ in the fractional voltage expression (Eq. 16) and utilize the reduction identity ($E_1(z)=e^z$) with the argument $z=-t/(RC)$, Eq. (16) turns into Eq. (23).

For $\alpha=1$ and $C_\alpha=C$ Eq. (22) turns into Eq. (24).

$$i_C(t) = \frac{V_{DC}}{R} E_1 \left(-\frac{t^1}{RC_1} \right) = \frac{V_{DC} e^{-t/(RC)}}{R} \quad (30)$$

This final expression is identical to the classical capacitor current equation.

4. The Energy Loss of the Circuit

Using the Caputo solution, the energy loss of the circuit during charging is given as

$$E_{Loss} = \int_0^T v_R(t) i_{C_\alpha}(t) dt \quad (31)$$

$$E_{Loss} = \int_0^T V_{dc} E_\alpha \left(-\frac{t^\alpha}{RC_\alpha} \right) \frac{V_{dc}}{R} E_\alpha \left(-\frac{t^\alpha}{RC_\alpha} \right) dt \quad (32)$$

where T is the charging time.

Let $\lambda=1/(RC_\alpha)$

$$E_{Loss} = \frac{(V_{dc})^2}{R} \int_0^T [E_\alpha(-\lambda t^\alpha)]^2 dt \quad (33)$$

If we use the following double series,

$$[E_\alpha(-\lambda t^\alpha)]^2 = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\lambda)^{k+m} \Gamma^{\alpha(k+m)}}{\Gamma(\alpha k + 1) \Gamma(\alpha m + 1)} \quad (34)$$

If we take the integral,

$$\int_0^T \tau^{\alpha(k+m)} d\tau = \frac{T^{1+\alpha(k+m)}}{1+\alpha(k+m)} \quad (35)$$

A convenient analytic form is the convergent double-series:

$$\frac{(-\lambda)^{k+m} \Gamma^{\alpha(k+m)+1}}{\Gamma(\alpha k + 1) \Gamma(\alpha m + 1) [\alpha(k+m)+1]} \quad (36)$$

As a check, for $\alpha=1$ one obtains,

$$\Gamma(\alpha k + 1) = \Gamma(k+1) = k! \quad (37)$$

Let $n=k+m$. Then for each fixed n , the index k runs from 0 to n .

$$E_{loss}(T) = \frac{(V_{dc})^2}{R} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\lambda)^n T^{1+n}}{1+n} \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{1}{k!(n-k)!} \quad (38)$$

If we expand the factorial,

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \frac{1}{k!(n-k)!} = \frac{1}{n!} \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} = \frac{2^n}{n!} \quad (39)$$

If we substitute Eq. (38) into Eq. (39),

$$E_{loss}(T) = \frac{(V_{dc})^2}{R} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\lambda)^n T^{1+n}}{1+n} \cdot \frac{2^n}{n!} = \frac{(V_{dc})^2}{R} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-2\lambda)^n T^{1+n}}{n!} \cdot \frac{T^{1+n}}{1+n} \quad (40)$$

Let's write the series in closed form,

$$\frac{T^{1+n}}{1+n} = \int_0^T \tau^n d\tau \quad (41)$$

Thus, each term in the series may be written in integral form.

$$\frac{(-2\lambda)^n T^{1+n}}{n!} \cdot \frac{T^{1+n}}{1+n} = \int_0^T \frac{(-2\lambda)^n}{n!} \tau^n d\tau \quad (42)$$

By interchanging the summation and integration,

$$E_{loss}(T) = \frac{(V_{dc})^2}{R} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \int_0^T \frac{(-2\lambda\tau)^n}{n!} \tau^n d\tau \quad (43)$$

The inner series is equal to the exponential series, so,

$$E_{loss}(T) = \frac{(V_{dc})^2}{R} \int_0^T e^{-2\lambda\tau} d\tau \quad (44)$$

If we solve the integral,

$$E_{loss}(T) = \frac{(V_{dc})^2}{R} \cdot \frac{1 - e^{-2\lambda T}}{2\lambda} = \frac{(V_{dc})^2}{2R\lambda} (1 - e^{-2\lambda T}) \quad (45)$$

and $T \rightarrow \infty$ yields the classical result, the energy loss in the resistor during charging is only dependent on the supply voltage and given as

$$E_{loss} = \frac{1}{2} C (V_{dc})^2 = \frac{C_{\alpha} V_c^2}{2} \quad (46)$$

The stored energy in the fractional capacitor of the is given as

$$E_{C_{\alpha}} = \int_0^{\infty} v_{C_{\alpha}}(t) i_{C_{\alpha}}(t) dt \quad (47)$$

$$E_{C_{\alpha}} = \int_0^{\infty} V_{dc} \left(1 E_{\alpha} \left(-\frac{t^{\alpha}}{RC_{\alpha}} \right) \right) \frac{V_{dc}}{R} E_{\alpha} \left(-\frac{t^{\alpha}}{RC_{\alpha}} \right) dt \quad (48)$$

$$E_{C_{\alpha}} = \frac{(V_{dc})^2}{R} \int_0^{\infty} E_{\alpha} \left(-\frac{t^{\alpha}}{RC_{\alpha}} \right) - \left(E_{\alpha} \left(-\frac{t^{\alpha}}{RC_{\alpha}} \right) \right)^2 dt \quad (49)$$

Let $\lambda = 1/(RC_{\alpha})$;

$$E_{C_{\alpha}} = \frac{(V_{dc})^2}{R} \int_0^{\infty} E_{\alpha}(-\lambda t^{\alpha}) - (E_{\alpha}(-\lambda t^{\alpha}))^2 dt \quad (50)$$

$$E_{C_{\alpha}} = \frac{(V_{dc})^2}{R} \int_0^{\infty} E_{\alpha}(-\lambda t^{\alpha}) - \int_0^{\infty} (E_{\alpha}(-\lambda t^{\alpha}))^2 dt \quad (51)$$

$$E_{C_{\alpha}} = \frac{(V_{dc})^2}{R} \int_0^{\infty} E_{\alpha}(-\lambda t^{\alpha}) - E_{loss} dt \quad (52)$$

$$E_{\alpha}(-\lambda t^{\alpha}) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\lambda)^k t^{\alpha k}}{\Gamma(\alpha k + 1)} \quad (53)$$

If we substitute Eq. 53 into Eq.54,

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^T E_{\alpha}(-\lambda t^{\alpha}) dt &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\lambda)^k}{\Gamma(\alpha k + 1)} \int_0^T t^{\alpha k} dt = \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\lambda)^k T^{\alpha k + 1}}{\Gamma(\alpha k + 1)(\alpha k + 1)} \end{aligned} \quad (54)$$

$$E_{C_{\alpha}}(T) = \frac{(V_{dc})^2}{R} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-\lambda)^k T^{\alpha k + 1}}{\Gamma(\alpha k + 1)(\alpha k + 1)} - E_{loss}(T) \quad (55)$$

Taking the limit $T \rightarrow \infty$, the asymptotic stored energy in the fractional-order capacitor is obtained as,

$$E_{C_{\alpha}} = \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} E_{C_{\alpha}}(T) \quad (56)$$

From (45) and (55), it is clear that the stored energy and the lost energy satisfy

$$E_{C_{\alpha}}(T) + E_{loss}(T) = \frac{(V_{dc})^2}{R} \int_0^T E_{\alpha}(-\lambda t^{\alpha}) dt \quad (57)$$

Thus, the total energy supplied by the source is split into the energy stored in the capacitor and the energy dissipated in the resistor.

For the classical case $\alpha=1$, since the capacitor behaves as an LTI element.

Substituting $V_C(t) = V_{DC}(1 - e^{-t/(RC)})$ and

$i_C(t) = \frac{V_{DC}e^{-t/(RC)}}{R}$ into the stored energy equation:

$$E_C = \frac{(V_{dc})^2}{R} \int_0^\infty [e^{-t/(RC)} - e^{-2t/(RC)}] dt = \frac{1}{2} CV_{dc}^2 \quad (58)$$

This confirms that the fractional stored-energy expression reduces to the well-known classical result when $\alpha=1$.

The energy efficiency $\eta(t)$ during charging can be calculated as:

$$\eta(t) = \frac{E_{C\alpha}}{E_{C\alpha} + E_R} \quad (59)$$

As presented in [24], when a capacitor charges from zero to the supply voltage, the total energy required equals the sum of the energy dissipated in the resistor and the energy radiated into the surrounding environment. The study in [24] also shows that this energy requirement does not depend on the series resistor illustrated in Figure 2. Even if the resistor varies with time, the result remains unchanged. The energy efficiency of this charging process is always fifty percent, meaning that half of the supplied energy is inevitably lost when charging a capacitor from a constant voltage source. However, this behavior differs in the case of the fractional-order capacitor and resistor series circuit. If α is different from one, time-dependent energy loss and stored energy formulas are obtained.

5. Simulation Results

In this section, the simulation results obtained using Python are presented. Using the circuit parameters listed in Table 1. The voltage and current waveforms of the fractional capacitor and resistor are sketched in Figures 3 and 4 for four different α values provided that alpha values are selected in the range of $0 < \alpha \leq 1$.

Table 1. Circuit Parameters used in the simulations.

V_{dc}	10 V
R	1 Ω
C_α	1 F/s $^{1-\alpha}$

Source: Authors.

Figure 3: The capacitor voltage $v_{C\alpha}(t)$ for four different alpha values of the fractional order α .

Source: Authors.

Figure 4: The current $i_{C\alpha}(t)$ versus time for four different values of the fractional order α .

Source: Authors.

In Figure 5, the energy loss in the circuit is shown. For $\alpha = 1$ this energy loss is the smallest, and as the value of α decreases, it can be observed to increase monotonically with time. For $\alpha = 1$ the lost energy rises most rapidly and then stabilizes. The smaller the value of α , the greater the amount of energy consumed. In Figure 6, the energy stored in the capacitor is shown. For $\alpha = 1$ the stored energy is the highest. It can be observed that the stored energy increases monotonically with time. After 0.75 seconds, as the value of α decreases, the stored energy takes smaller values. The smaller the value of α , the more rapidly the stored energy rises before 0.75 seconds. At 5 seconds, it can be seen that for values of α different from 1 the system has not yet reached a steady state.

Figure 5: The energy loss $E_{loss}(t)$ versus time for four different values of the fractional order α .

Source: Authors.

Figure 6: The stored energy $E_{C\alpha}(t)$ versus time for four different values of the fractional order α .

Source: Authors.

For $\alpha = 1$, at 20 seconds the energy efficiency is 0.5, as shown in [26]. This represents the smallest energy evolution among all α values. It can be observed that the smaller the value of α , the greater the energy efficiency. For $\alpha = 0.3$, the energy evolution reaches 70%. The simulation results demonstrate that the charging energy efficiency of fractional-order capacitors is higher than that of the LTI capacitors.

Figure 7: The energy efficiency $\eta(t)$ versus time for four different values of the fractional order α .

Source: Authors.

6. Conclusions

In this study, a method is proposed to calculate the energy lost in the resistor of a first-order (FO) capacitor–resistor circuit supplied by a DC voltage source, using time-domain expressions for voltage and current obtained through circuit analysis. The resulting energy loss expression involves a special function known as the Mittag-Leffler function E_α . The solutions of the circuit variables and energy-related equations for the circuit are simulated using Python. It is demonstrated that the charging efficiency of the FO capacitor depends on both the fractional-order parameter α and the resistance of the series resistor. Notably, the efficiency can exceed 50%, which is the theoretical value for an LTI capacitor under similar conditions. The energy efficiency of the circuit is higher than 50% for the examined circuit if α is less than one. It is important to emphasize that the formulas derived here is specific to the examined configuration and cannot be directly applied to circuits with different sources or topologies. As a novel circuit element, the FO capacitor requires further analysis when

integrated with other circuit components and subjected to various input waveforms with a nonzero average. For each distinct circuit topology, the energy of the F0 capacitor must be recalculated using a similar methodology to the one presented in this work.

This study also demonstrates that a purely voltage-dependent energy formula is insufficient due to the inherent time dependence of FO systems since the capacitor voltage is found as dependent on a time series not on the capacitor voltage explicitly.

Authors Contribution: Conceive – Reşat Mutlu (R.M.), Design – R.M., Berk Mercan (B.M.), Alperen Hoçur (A.H.), Supervision – R.M.; Data Collection and/or Processing – B.M., A.H.,R.M.; Analysis and/or Interpretation – B.M., A.H.,R.M.; Literature Review – R.M., Writer - B.M., A.H.,R.M.; Critical Reviews – B.M., A.H.,R.M.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors have declared no conflicts of interest.

References

- [1] Gutierrez R. E., Rosário J. M., Tenreiro Machado J. Fractional order calculus: basic concepts and engineering applications . *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, volume 2010(1), pages 375858. (2010).
- [2] Moreles M. A., Lainez R. Mathematical modelling of fractional order circuit elements and bioimpedance applications . *Communications in Nonlinear Science and Numerical Simulation*, volume 46, pages 81–88. (2017).
- [3] Kothari K., Mehta U. V., Prasad R. Fractional-order system modeling and its applications . *Journal of Engineering Science and Technology Review*, volume 12(6), pages 1–10. (2019).
- [4] Freeborn T. J. A survey of fractional-order circuit models for biology and biomedicine . *IEEE Journal on Emerging and Selected Topics in Circuits and Systems*, volume 3, pages 416–424. (2013).
- [5] Ortigueira M. D., Martynyuk V., Kosenkov V., Batista A. G. A new look at the capacitor theory . *Fractal and Fractional*, volume 7(1), pages 86. (2023).
- [6] Adhikary A., Khanra M., Pal J., Biswas K. Realization of fractional order elements . *Inae Letters*, volume 2, pages 41–47. (2017).
- [7] Tsirimokou G., Kartci A., Koton J., Herencsar N., Psychalinos C. Comparative study of discrete component realizations of fractional-order capacitor and inductor active emulators . *Journal of Circuits, Systems and Computers*, volume 27, pages 1850170. (2018).
- [8] Freeborn T. J., Maundy B., Elwakil A. S. Measurement of supercapacitor fractional-order model parameters from voltage-excited step response . *IEEE Journal on Emerging and Selected Topics in Circuits and Systems*, volume 3, pages 367–376. (2013).
- [9] Freeborn T. J., Maundy B., Elwakil A. S. Fractional-order models of supercapacitors, batteries and fuel cells: a survey . *Materials for Renewable and Sustainable Energy*, volume 4, pages 1–7. (2015).
- [10] Lewandowski M., Orzyłowski M. Fractional-order models: The case study of the supercapacitor capacitance measurement . *Bulletin of the Polish Academy of Sciences: Technical Sciences*, pages 449–457. (2017).
- [11] Freeborn T. J., Elwakil A. S., Allagui A. Supercapacitor fractional-order model discharging from polynomial time-varying currents. In: *IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems (ISCAS)*, pages 1–5. IEEE. (2018).
- [12] Hidalgo-Reyes J. I., Gómez-Aguilar J. F., Escobar-Jiménez R. F., Alvarado-Martínez V. M., López-López M. G. Classical and fractional-order modeling of equivalent electrical circuits for supercapacitors and batteries, energy management strategies for hybrid systems and methods for the state of charge estimation: A state of the art review . *Microelectronics Journal*, volume 85, pages 109–128. (2019).
- [13] Kartci A., Agambayev A., Herencsar N., Salama K. N. Series-, parallel-, and inter-connection of solid-state arbitrary fractional-order capacitors: theoretical study and experimental verification . *IEEE Access*, volume 6, pages 10933–10943. (2018).
- [14] Sikora R. Fractional derivatives in electrical circuit theory—critical remarks . *Archives of Electrical Engineering*, volume 66, pages 155–163. (2017).

[15] Morales-Delgado V. F., Gómez-Aguilar J. F., Taneco-Hernandez M. A. Analytical solutions of electrical circuits described by fractional conformable derivatives in Liouville-Caputo sense.

AEU-International Journal of Electronics and Communications, volume 85, pages 108–117 (2018)

[16] Martínez L., Rosales J. J., Carreño C. A. Electrical circuits described by fractional conformable derivative. *International Journal of Circuit Theory and Applications*, volume 46, pages 1091–1100. (2018).

[17] Gómez-Aguilar J. F. Fundamental solutions to electrical circuits of non-integer order via fractional derivatives with and without singular kernels. *The European Physical Journal Plus*, volume 133, pages 197. (2018).

[18] Piotrowska E. Analysis the conformable fractional derivative and Caputo definitions in the action of an electric circuit containing a supercapacitor. In: *Proc. SPIE 10808, Photonics Applications in Astronomy, Communications, Industry, and High-Energy Physics Experiments*, pages 108081T. (2018).

[19] Elwakil A. S. Fractional-order circuits and systems: An emerging interdisciplinary research area. *IEEE Circuits and Systems Magazine*, volume 10(4), pages 40–50. (2010).

[20] Gómez-Aguilar J. F., Yépez-Martínez H., Escobar-Jiménez R. F., Astorga-Zaragoza C. M., Reyes-Reyes J. Analytical and numerical solutions of electrical circuits described by fractional derivatives. *Applied Mathematical*

Modelling, volume 40(21-22), pages 9079–9094. (2016).

[21] Zhang B., Shu X. Fractional-order electrical circuit theory. Springer Singapore. (2022).

[22] Sumper A., Baggini A. Electrical energy efficiency: technologies and applications. John Wiley & Sons, West Sussex, United Kingdom. (2012).

[23] Cheung C. K., Tan S. C., Chi K. T., Ioinovici A. On energy efficiency of switched-capacitor converters. *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, volume 28(2), pages 862–876. (2012).

[24] Fouda M. E., Elwakil A. S., Radwan A. G., Allagui A. Power and energy analysis of fractional order electrical energy storage devices. *Energy*, volume 111, pages 785–792. (2016).

[25] Halliday D., Resnick R., Walker J. Fundamentals of Physics. John Wiley & Sons, New York, USA. (2014).

[26] Abu-Labdeh A. M., Al-Jaber S. M. Energy consideration from non-equilibrium to equilibrium state in the process of charging a capacitor. *Journal of Electrostatics*. (2008).

[27] Kopka R. Estimation of supercapacitor energy storage based on fractional differential equations. *Nanoscale Research Letters*, volume 12, pages 636. (2017).

[28] Palaz U., Mutlu R. Energy Consideration of a Capacitor Modelled Using Conformal Fractional-Order Derivative. *Kocaeli Journal of Science and Engineering*, volume 5(2), pages 117–125. (2022).